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The Organization of Professional Development of Specialists of the Sociocultural Centers for Children: Towns of Professions, Parks of Science, Interactive Museums

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Abstract

The article analyzes education and leisure centers for children, the edutainment-centers. The focus is on the development of new social culture, an increase of the demand in edutainment-centers, problems of competency-based development and profiles of experts' competencies, including their vocational training at corporate and university programs.

The purpose of the research is to study the institutional development of edutainment-centers, identify their differences and advantages from traditional institutions (schools), analyze the features of developing technologies in edutainment-centers as well as the features of teacher training according to corporate standards.

As a result of the study, the features of the institutional and geographical development of the edutainment-centers, the features of educational environment for children, the features of the programs for children, the features of the teacher training programs for the edutainment-centers, the specifics of the development of future competencies in children in the edutainment-centers are characterized.

The practical significance of the study is new knowledge about the educational industry as an industry for the development of human potential.

Keywords: edutainment centers, corporate programs, professional development, sociocultural centers for children, cultural competencies, science parks, interactive museums.

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Introduction

Social and cultural centers (edutainment-center) of the non-governmental sector of additional education and leisure of children become a special task of entrepreneurial and professional pedagogical initiatives. Thanks to the initiatives of the entrepreneurial and business communities over the past five years, the market for socio-cultural and educational services for children has been intensively developed: towns of professions, science parks, and interactive museums.

However, against the background of intensive development of socio-cultural and cultural-educational centers in the edutainment sector, a lack of research data on the conditions and development trends of the new sector, on the problem of training teachers for such centers, which require completely different pedagogical competencies than at school, is noted.

These tasks become even more relevant in the context of amendments to the Federal Law “On Education in the Russian Federation” (Government of the Russian Federation, 2012) regarding the organization of the provision of additional education for children both in state educational organizations and in private organizations implementing additional general educational and sociocultural programs for children.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the research is to study the institutional development of centers, to identify their differences and advantages from traditional institutions (schools), to analyze the features of developing technologies in centers, the features of the training of teaching staff for centers according to corporate standards. As a result of the study, the features of the institutional and geographical development of the centers, the features of creating a developing environment for children, the features of the developing programs for children, the features of the training of pedagogical staff for the centers, the specifics of the development of future competencies in children in the centers are characterized. The practical significance of the study is new knowledge about the educational industry of the future as an industry for the development of human potential.

Literature review

The amendments to the law are aimed at solving the problem stipulated by the Executive Order on Implementing State Policy in Science and Education, No. 599 (2012) to increase by 2020 the number of children aged 5 to 18 years studying in additional educational programs in the total number of children this age up to 70–75%. The changes taking place both in the development of new sociocultural centers - non-

governmental organizations and practices of continuing education, and in the change in the state's position regarding the support of private organizations and the development of public-private partnerships, actualize the need for research data on the development of the edutainment sector for making sound management and investment decisions, as well as to form the views of stakeholders on the development of new markets for educational services, new practices and training teachers to implement these new practices.

In foreign pedagogy edutainment is already widespread. In 1973, Robert Heyman first mentioned education in a report to the National Geographic Society (Heyman & Parnall, 1973). In Russia, the concept of practice of introduction has been introduced relatively recently. And as in the journalistic texts of the media: the "New Park Culture" portal, where it is proposed to divide the edutainment sector into 2 parts "the first is when you mean the way of transferring information and skills to those who are not too motivated (Brown & Bimrose, 2014). Here, entertainment is seen as a way to sweeten the pill. The second is when the learning process itself is understood as entertainment and information and skills can be extracted from a variety of sources, including those that were not originally intended as educational materials. The first, respectively, implies a passive perception of information and the second – active search". The popular Internet publication MEL speaks about the usefulness of using the potential of the edutainment sector to develop children's skills: "Most of the skills for life are acquired by children in the game. Gaming education, edutainment is also a fast-growing business. In the game it is really possible (and easier) to teach reading, writing and counting, to remember any information, to acquire any skill, to master any mental actions. The secret of the game is that motivation is already hidden inside" (Remorenko, 2016).

The situation of the development of sociocultural centers of the edutainment sector also attracts the attention of Russian researchers. So, for example, Shaykhlislamova (2017) speaks about the expansion of pedagogical opportunities in increasing the motivation of the child, when using edutainment technology. Karmalova and Khankeeva (2016) in their article "Entertainment: a concept, specificity, study of the needs of the target audience", they say: "Entertainment is a modern sociocultural technology for the development of children, which has a number of methodological advantages and prospects. However, one cannot deny the fact that education is not an alternative to academic education. This technology is an additional option, an interesting way to gain new knowledge".

Methodology

The methodological basis of the study was:

- 1) The theory of creative industries "Creative industries" (Landry, 2012) and specialized industries (Porter, 1980; Marshall, 2010).

- 2) The concept of the structure of the creative industry 4: 0 (Van Heur, 2019).
- 3) Concepts of developing children's education as an open sociocultural space and environment of self-determination (Moeglin, 2018).

The research methodology is based on the methods of content analysis of developing programs of edutainment centers, the methods of factor analysis of dialogue and socio-cultural competencies in children, the method of comparative analysis of the institutions of edutainment centers and schools, and the method of statistical analysis.

For the period 2015-2018 we investigated the development of new sociocultural centers-edutainment using survey methods, interviewing teachers and managerial towns of professions and interactive museums, as well as using focus group methods, questioning consumers of edutainment services, a method of content analysis of corporate teacher training programs for socio-cultural centers (Fiofanova, 2018).

Results

Despite the fact that the concept of “edutainment” appeared in Russia recently, we see that interest in this phenomenon is growing. And according to the results of interviews of the township managers of the professions of Kidburg, Kidzania, Masterslavl, managers of science parks and interactoriums: Mars-Tefo, Experimentanium, Tecla-park and others, it was revealed that these socio-cultural centers have a shortage of teaching staff and a lack of professional competencies necessary for the implementation of socio-cultural and educational activities precisely in these centers, since the teacher of the sociocultural center-edutainment performs slightly different functions than in school, this is due to the use of other technologies.

Edutainment technology is based on such organizational and pedagogical techniques as:

Event-Based Learning – such an approach in the organization of the pedagogical process, when the process of child development is built on events. Such events may include creative festivals, intellectual competitions, fairs of technologies and achievements, etc. The child acts here as the creator, subject of action and hero of the event.

Learning Through Storytelling – a way to build a child’s development process in the form of history Effective supply of developing material will help provide software products. The plot design can be arranged in the form of sms, comics, online correspondence, videos, travel books, etc.

Threshold Concepts – pedagogical technique that breaks the threshold representations of students. Its essence boils down to encouraging children to look at the problem under study with different eyes. For example, bewildered by absurd reasoning, show how chemical and physical processes manifest themselves every day in the kitchen, show 3-d reactions on Mars, etc. Such a technique helps to connect science with practice, to problematize the sociocultural context of child development.

Thematic Education – this is the principle in which the learning process is built not within the framework of disciplines or subjects, but within the framework of an interdisciplinary topic (Edutainment as Modern Technology, 2020).

Today, the most common formats of sociocultural centers are science parks, towns of professions and interactoriums (interactive museums). In 2011, in Russia there was only 1 fleet of professions, and there were 4 pieces of interactive science museums. By 2017, the number of profession parks increased to 40, and more than 90 interactive museums.

Organizational forms of classes with children in socio-cultural centers-edutainment: master classes, laboratory work, career-oriented games, science shows, tours, lectures, quests, etc.

Due to the fact that organizational principles, and developing technologies, and the structure of the content of developing activities, and the forms of communication with children in edutainment socio-cultural centers are different from school ones, therefore teachers with a different type and profile of competencies are in demand in socio-cultural centers. The problem is that universities do not have enough higher education programs that would ensure the staff development of the edutainment industry. Many townships of professions, science parks, interactive museums develop their corporate programs for professional development of personnel, their standards for certification of professional competencies of teachers of socio-cultural centers-edutainment.

The content analysis of corporate programs of sociocultural centers-edutainment made it possible to identify key competencies in the profile of competencies of teachers of townships, science parks, and interactive museums. It is these competencies that are the subject of professional development in corporate programs and the subject of certification for employment in sociocultural centers-edutainment.

General cultural competencies:

- able to apply modern communication technologies, including in a foreign language (s);
- able to analyze and take into account the diversity of cultures in the process of intercultural interaction;

- knows how to ethically resolve a conflict situation;
- analyzes the working situation, carries out current and final control, assessment and correction of their own activities;
- understands the need for constant self-development, develops skills for the constant expansion of one's own knowledge.

General professional competencies:

- knows how to organize pedagogical support for the child's self-determination in a situation of choice;
- knows how to maintain a dialogue with the child, depending on his interests and on topics of interest to him;
- knows how to organize groups of children according to their interests, cooperation in groups and social interaction of children;
- organizes developing technologies of interactive classes according to the principles and technologies of sociocultural centers-edutainment.

Special professional competencies:

- knows how to methodically competently develop a new developmental program for children in the territory of the profession town, science park, interactorium (a new educational route or a new educational topic in the sociocultural environment of profession towns, science parks, interactoriums);
- owns modern methods, forms, means and technologies of interactive classes; targeted assistance to children;
- knows how: to use knowledge about the developmental features of students for planning interactive classes; apply educational technologies to individualize classes.

The organization of professional development of personnel of sociocultural centers-edutainment is most often carried out in the form of corporate programs of professional development in profession towns, science parks and interactive museums. Also, for 2017-2018. Master's programs in this profile of training professionals began to be created at universities. For example: higher education educational program "Event-technologies in the creative leisure industry" (Kiseleva, 2020), implemented at the Institute of

Culture and Arts of the Moscow City Pedagogical University, as well as the higher education educational program “Designing Urban Educational Infrastructures” (Ivanova, 2020), implemented at the institute of system projects of this university. Higher education educational program “Psychology (profile: intercultural communication)” is being implemented at Moscow State University.

The content of these programs is structured for relevant tasks and educational results and includes such courses as: “Phenomenology of educational infrastructure”, “Educational potential of edutainment practices”, “Assessment of development results in edutainment programs”, “Creative pedagogy”, “Educational underground”, “Producing educational projects”, “Studying the development trends of international and Russian educational infrastructures”, “Designing and redesigning the socio-cultural and educational environment”.

As part of the training, students practice in Kidburg, Kidzania, Mars-Tefo, Experimentium, Tesla Museum, and Projectorium.

To enter the edutainment socio-cultural center, students undergo certification of qualifications according to the corporate standards of edutainment centers.

Discussion

To assess the quality of training professionals for sociocultural centers-edutainment, we used interviews of city managers of professions, science parks and interactoriums, as well as factor analysis of feedback from parents and children on the otzovik.com.

The managers of edutainment sociocultural centers and the parents of children attending edutainment centers note the ability to interest children in science, a profession, and a specific topic as positive results of the professional development of teachers at edutainment centers. Many respondents said that teachers of edutainment centers contribute to the formation of children's interest, which will ensure that the child begins to plunge deeper into some area (science, study of the city, profession). Kidburg manager:

We don't say that we are engaged in career guidance, but we hope that children will leave here inspired by the atmosphere of a profession and with emphasis on choosing it.

Masterslavl manager:

Even if a child comes to us in two years for all of our 5 physics programs that will take place in these two years, he is unlikely to learn physics, but at least he will expand some ideas, some kind

of more scientific look at peace. The main thing is that he will have an interest in these things and then he can already study it on his own, at some specialized circles and so on.

The manager of the Experimentium:

Our goal is to interest children in the study of sciences, that science is not just numbers, formulas, but that it is interesting and there is practical application for this.

Another important competence of edutainment-center teachers who consider camp managers of professions, science parks and interactoriums is: the creation of conditions for the socialization of children, integration into the adult world, career guidance. The manager of Kidzania:

This is, of course, socialization. Because here he played with his guys, with his friends, in a completely different way – a fireman...

Career guidance elements in the occupation park are also noted by parents. Judging by the reviews from special sites where you can describe your impressions, advantages and disadvantages of organizations (<http://otzovik.com/>), parents note a variety of activities (tests of professions), which is important for them at an early age:

My seven-year-old the daughter already knows who she will be when she grows up, a teacher. In Kidzania, a child is filled in a citizen's passport, given a receipt for the initial capital, a city map and a memo of professions. After visiting the exchange you need to go to the bank to exchange the receipt for the pros. We got the money, now we're going to the hospital for a physical examination. Here, of course, everything is individual and depends on the child.

Another mother notes the possibilities of understanding adulthood “playfully”:

I must say that the details are thought out perfectly. If the fire department, then the fire is going to extinguish by car and the impromptu fire is really extinguished. If you work in the ambulance, then by car with a flasher they go to help people. If mail, then really children deliver and deliver mail and parcels to organizations. Everything is like in adulthood. This is a big world for little ones. Children understood a great life effortlessly ... So, the positive aspects: a fundamentally new leisure for children, the opportunity to learn a particular profession, to understand how it works, familiarity with adult life, a unique interior that repeats the "big life".

It is worth noting that the format of the children's park of professions is included in the “5 formats of career guidance practiced throughout the world” (Borodai, Kolesnikova, & Nikitina, 2020). Parents also note one of the important competencies of an edutainment-center teacher – creating conditions for parents to communicate with their children and share leisure activities (typical for all formats except towns of professions where parents, as a rule, do not participate). The manager of Kidburg:

Communication, communication, which results from interactivity; family leisure, i.e. parent involvement. Parents can be present at all classes, they can participate, and we need to work on this further, it is very important.

Parent review:

And when the child and I leave, we communicate with him in the same language and on an interesting topic, come home, tell dad and brothers about what we saw, hear, start arguing, discussing, also on the Internet too looking for information. It's very interesting, that is, if we watched a movie in a movie theater, then maybe it was not so useful for our children.

Conclusion

Thus, we can conclude that in society there is a demand for new professional competencies of pedagogical specialists, the growth in demand is associated with the creation of new developing sociocultural practices and a new sociocultural industry of edutainment centers. At the same time, the vocational education system must flexibly and quickly respond to changes in the labor market and design popular professional education programs.

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